

“EFFECT OF FAMILY ENVIRONMENT ON LEARNING STRATEGIES OF ADULT LEARNERS PURSUING EQUIVALANCY PROGRAMME IN KERALA.”

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Abstract:

In the present study the investigator made an attempt to assess the Effect of Family Environment on learning strategies of adult learners pursuing equivalency programme in Kerala. Descriptive survey method was adopted for the study. The sample consist 489 adult learners and statistical technique used for the study were Pearson's Product moment coefficient oft correlation.. Results indicate that there exist a significant positive relationship between 'Learning Strategies' and Family Environment of Adult Learners pursuing Equivalency programme.

INTRODUCTION

Kerala is the first complete literate state in India. It achieved this great target on 18th April, 1991. Though several decades crossed after the declaration of complete literacy in Kerala, the neo literates became illiterate in course of time due to lack of practice and absence of opportunity to continue their studies through a meaningful post-literacy programmes. The major causes of relapse of illiteracy may be due to the time gap between conclusion of the basic literacy phase and beginning of post-literacy phase. Hence, the National Literacy Mission realized the need for launching post-literacy programmes and designed a scheme of continuing education. This has been approved by Government of India and come in to force from 1st January 1996. The scheme has divided the Continuing Education programme in to four categories-Equivalency Programme (EPs), Income Generating Programmes (IGPs), Quality of Life Improving Programmes (QLIPs) and Individual Interest Promotion Programmes. UNESCO (2006) also reported that “the formal education system does not meet these urgency of providing

education for all especially for out of school population. For to meet this need, UNESCO suggest different policies and strategies .i.e., lifelong and continuing education programme like Equivalency Programme.”

This is the context in which Kerala State Literacy Mission Authority launched an educational programme called ‘Equivalency Learning Programme’ on 26th January 1999. It gives opportunity for neo-literates and dropouts of formal school to enrol in Equivalency programme and achieving certificate equivalent to the formal education. It leads to opening of the new horizons of higher education for neo literates and adult learners who are dropout from formal stream of education.

NEED AND SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Under Equivalency programme, the learners are heterogeneous- with respect to age, gender, socio-economic status and so on. The tastes, interest and family background of the learners in group may vary widely. Majority of them are the major economic source of family and have not got adequate environment for learning due to job related and family related engagements. Thus time become an elephant in the room for the learners, who pursue Equivalency Programme. Lack of time doesn't allow them to approach the learning material reflectively and critically. Higher order learning skills faces serious challenges for these learners. This leads to mugging up of information and cramming. As a result, the participants of Equivalency Programme start complaining about their own inefficiency in remembering the information taught to them.

Good number of studies proved that strategic learning can improve student's performance. A number of studies identified strong relationship between learning strategies and achievement (Lenz & Hughes, 1990; Graham, et al., 1991; Miller and Mercer,1993 ;Bulgren,et al.,1995 and Lee, et al.,1999). Studies of Hughes and Schumaker, (1991), Moody and Raymond (1993) shows that strong relation with

strategic learning and student's performance. Though there is a plethora of literature about the effect of learning strategies on various dimensions of student, it is hard to find such studies related to adult learners. This shows grave negligence about the learning related issues of adult learning. It may not be an exaggeration to say that researches on learning related issues of adult learners is a neglected area. In India such negligence has magnified effect. Kerala being the first state to execute Equivalency Programme, under literacy mission, such studies carry vital importance. This is the context in which this study is carried out.

The investigator could not find any studies related to Learning Strategies and factors influencing Learning Strategies of adult learners. This has led the investigator, take up the present study entitled as “*Effect of Family Environment on Learning Strategies of Adult learners pursuing Equivalency programme in Kerala.*”

OBJECTIVES

To test whether there exist any significant relationship between the Family Environment and Learning Strategies of adult learners pursuing equivalency programme for the total sample and sub-samples selected for the study.

HYPOTHESES

There will be significant relationship between the Family Environment and Learning Strategies of adult learners pursuing equivalency programme for the total sample and sub-samples selected for the study.

METHODOLOGY

The methodology followed by the investigator is discussed below:

VARIABLES FOR THE STUDY

Independent variables selected for the present study is Family Environment and Dependent variable for the study is Learning Strategies of adult learners pursuing Equivalency Programme. Demographic variables selected for the study are gender(male/female),

locale(rural/urban),maritalstatus(married/unmarried),employmentstatus(employed/unemployed) and category – General, O.B.C and SC/ST.

SAMPLE FOR THE STUDY

The present study is intended to carry out on a representative sample of 439 Adult learners pursuing equivalency classes for 10th standard level at, Malappuram district of Kerala state. The sample will be drawn by cluster random sampling technique giving due representation to factors like gender, locale, marital status, employment status and category.

TOOLS AND TECHNIQUE USED IN THE STUDY

Two instruments are used for the data collection of the study. Out of these, Learning Strategy Scale for Adult Learners was developed and standardized by the investigator with the help of Research Supervisor. Family EnvironmentScale(Bhatia,H.&Chadha,N.H,1993) are the adopted tools used for the study.

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUE USED FOR THE STUDY

The present study used Pearson's Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation to identify the relationship between independent and dependent variable.

Statistical Analysis

Correlation of Learning Strategy and each of Independent variables of adult learners pursuing Equivalency Programme for the Total sample

The details of correlation between 'Learning Strategies' and each of the Independent variables. viz Family Environment, Emotional Intelligence, Socio Economic Status and Job Involvement of adult learners pursuing Equivalency programme for the total sample are presented in the Table.

Table No.1

Relationship between Learning Strategies and Family Environment, Emotional Intelligence, Socio Economic Status and Job Involvement of adult learners pursuing Equivalency Programme for Total sample

Independent variables	N	r	Level of significance	Confidence interval		Shared variance
				Lower limit	Upper limit	
Family environment	439	0.990**	0.001	0.988	0.992	98.01

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Interpretation of findings

For the total sample, the correlation between Family Environment and Learning strategies are 0.990, which is found to be significant ($p < 0.01$). Hence the relationship between these two variables is considered to be real. The relationship can be verbally interpreted as high correlation. The obtained correlation is positive, this means that increase in one variable results a corresponding increase in the other variable. Hence any increase in Family Environment results in increase in Learning Strategies of adult learners.

The 0.01 confidence interval for the total sample is found to be between 0.988 and 0.992. This shows that if the correlation is worked out for the same variable for the whole population, the resulting correlation will be between these intervals at 0.01 level of probability. The shared variance of Learning Strategies with Family Environment is 98.01. This means that 98.01 percent of what is measured by Family Environment is related to Learning Strategies.

Discussion

The coefficient of correlation estimated between 'Learning Strategies' and Family Environment of adult learners for the total sample is found to be

significant at 0.01 probability level, for the total sample. The value of 'r' is 0.990. The percentage of overlap is 98.01.

From these findings, it can be concluded that there exist a significant positive relationship between 'Learning Strategies' and Family Environment of adult learners pursuing Equivalency programme.

ESTIMATION OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN LEARNING STRATEGIES AND INDEPENDENT VARIABLES FOR THE SUBSAMPLE

The details of correlation between ' Learning Strategies' and Family environment for adult learners pursuing Equivalency programme for the sub samples.,viz Male, Female, Rural, Urban, Married, Unmarried, Employed, Unemployed, General, O.B.C and SC/ST category.

Correlation of Learning Strategies and Family environment for Male and Female adult learners pursuing Equivalency Programme

The details of correlation between Learning Strategies and Family Environment of Male adult learners pursuing Equivalency Programme are presented in the Table.

TABLE No. 2

Relationship between Learning Strategies and family environment for Male and Female Adult learners pursuing Equivalency Programme

Independent variables	N		r	Level of significance	Confidence interval		Shared variance
					Lower limit	Upper limit	
Family environment	Male	199	0.973**	0.001	0.962	0.981	94.67
	Female	240	0.972**	0.001	0.962	0.979	94.47

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Interpretation of findings

Family Environment and Learning strategies:- For the Male sample, the correlation between Family Environment and Learning strategy is 0.973, which is found to be significant($p < 0.01$). Hence the relationship between these two variables is considered to be real. The relationship can be verbally interpreted as very high correlation. The obtained correlation says that increase in one variable affecting the corresponding variable. Hence any increase in Family Environment results an increase in the Learning strategies of adult learners.

The confidence interval for the male sample is found to be between 0.962 and 0.981. This shows that if the correlation is worked out for the same variable for the whole population, the resulting correlation will be between these intervals at 0.01 level of probability. The shared variance of Learning Strategies with Family Environment is 94.67. This means that 94.67 percent of what is measured by Family Environment is related to Learning Strategies.

Family Environment and Learning strategies:- For the Female sample, the correlation between Family Environment and Learning strategy is 0.972, which is found to be significant($p < 0.01$). Hence the relationship between these two variables is considered to be real. The relationship can be verbally interpreted as very high correlation. The obtained correlation is positive; this means that increase in one variable result a corresponding increase in the other variable. Hence any increase in Family Environment results in increase in Learning strategies of adult learners.

The 0.01 confidence interval for the rural sample is found to be between 0.962 and 0.979. This shows that if the correlation is worked out for the same variable for the whole population, the resulting correlation will be between these intervals at 0.01 level of probability. The shared variance of Learning strategies with Family Environment is 94.47. This means that 94.47 percent of what is measured by Family Environment is related to Learning Strategies.

Correlation of Learning Strategies and each of the Independent Variables for Rural and Urban adult learners pursuing Equivalency Programme

The details of correlation between Learning Strategies and Family Environment of Rural and urban adult learners pursuing Equivalency Programme are presented in the Table No.3

TABLE No. 3

Relationship between Learning Strategies and family environment for Rural and Urban Adult learners pursuing Equivalency Programme

Independent variables	N		r	Level of significance	Confidence interval		Shared variance
					Lower limit	Upper limit	
Family environment	Rural	313	0.571**	0.001	0.465	0.661	32.69
	Urban	126	0.984**	0.001	0.975	0.989	96.83

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Interpretation of findings

a) Family Environment and Learning strategies:-For the Rural sample, the correlation between Family Environment and Learning strategy is 0.571, which is found to be significant($p < 0.01$). Hence the relationship between these two variables is considered to be real. The relationship can be verbally interpreted as moderate correlation. The obtained correlation is positive, this means that increase in one variable result a corresponding increase in the other variable. Hence any increase in Family Environment results in increase in Learning strategies of adult learners.

The 0.01 confidence interval for the rural sample is found to be between 0.465 and 0.661. This shows that if the correlation is worked out for the same variable for the whole population, the resulting correlation will be between these intervals at 0.01 level of probability. The shared variance of Learning strategies

with Family Environment is 32.60. This means that 32.60 percent of what is measured by Family Environment is related to Learning Strategies.

Family Environment and Learning strategies:- For the urban sample, the correlation between Family Environment and Learning strategy is 0.984, which is found to be significant ($p < 0.01$). Hence the relationship between these two variables is considered to be real. The relationship can be verbally interpreted as high correlation. The obtained correlation is positive, this means that increase in one variable results a corresponding increase in the other variable. Hence any increase in Family Environment results in increase in Learning strategies of adult learners.

The 0.01 confidence interval for the total sample is found to be between 0.975 and 0.989. This shows that if the correlation is worked out for the same variable for the whole population, the resulting correlation will be between these intervals at 0.01 level of probability. The shared variance of Learning Strategies with Family Environment is 96.83. This means that 96.83 percent of what is measured by Family Environment is related to Learning Strategies.

Correlation of Learning Strategies and Family environment for Married and Unmarried adult learners pursuing Equivalency Programme

The details of correlation between Learning Strategies and Family Environment for Married and unmarried adult learners pursuing Equivalency programme are presented in the Table.

TABLE No. 4

Relationship between Learning Strategies and family environment for Married and Unmarried Adult learners pursuing Equivalency Programme

Independent variables	N		r	Level of significance	Confidence interval		Shared variance
					Lower limit	Upper limit	
Family environment	Married	30 4	0.986* *	0.001	0.982	0.989	97.21
	Unmarried	13 5	0.987* *	0.001	0.98	0.991	97.41

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Interpretation of findings

For the married sample, the correlation between Family Environment and Learning strategy is 0.986, which is found to be significant ($p < 0.01$). Hence the relationship between these two variables is considered to be real. The relationship can be verbally interpreted as very high correlation. The obtained correlation is positive, this means that increase in one variable result a corresponding increase in the other variable. Hence any increase in Family Environment results in increase in Learning strategies of adult learners.

The 0.01 confidence interval for the rural sample is found to be between 0.982 and 0.989. This shows that if the correlation is worked out for the same variable for the whole population, the resulting correlation will be between these intervals at 0.01 level of probability. The shared variance of Learning strategies with Family Environment is 97.21. This means that 97.21 percent of what is measured by Family Environment is related to Learning Strategies.

For the unmarried sample, the correlation between Family Environment and Learning strategy is 0.987, which is found to be significant ($p < 0.01$). Hence the relationship between these two variables is considered to be real. The relationship can be verbally interpreted as very high correlation. The obtained correlation give the meaning that there is significant relationship between two variables.. Hence an increase in Family Environment results an increase in the Learning strategies

of adult learners.

The confidence interval for the rural sample is found to be between 0.98 and 0.991. This shows that if the correlation is worked out for the same variable for the whole population, the resulting correlation will be between these intervals at 0.01 significant level of probability. The shared variance of Learning strategies with Family Environment is 97.41. This means that 97.41 percent of what is measured by Family Environment is related to Learning Strategies.

Discussion

For the Subsamples- locality, gender and marital status, the coefficient of correlation estimated between 'Learning Strategy' and Family Environment of adult learners are found to be significant at 0.01 probability level.

From these findings, it can be concluded that there exist significant positive relationship between 'Learning Strategy' and Family Environment of adult learners pursuing Equivalency Programme for the subsamples.

Research studies related to this area well supported these findings. Lawrence A. Kurdek (1988) administered a study which reveals that students with parents (father and mother) and nuclear families had attained better academic performance and less problematic behaviour in school than those of students who were brought out either in mother-custody or stepfather families. Fuligni (1997) explored the impact of family background, parental attitudes, peer support, and adolescents' own attitudes and behaviors on the academic achievement of students from immigrant families. Results indicated that first and second generation students received higher grades in mathematics and English than their peers from native families. Only a small portion of their success could be attributed to their socio-economic background; a more significant correlate of their achievement was a strong emphasis on education that was shared by the students, their parents, and their peers.

Thus the findings of the present study goes in line with established research results. More specifically, present study throw light in to the strong positive relationship between learning strategy and family environment of adult learners of Equivalency programme.

REFERENCES:

- Aggarwal, K.L. (1986). *A study of the effect of parental encouragement upon the educational development of the students*. (Ph.D. Thesis, Garhwal University). Retrieved from <http://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/bitstream/10603/13522/.pdf>
- Lenz, B. K. & Hughes, C. A. (1990). A word identification strategy for adolescents with learning disabilities. *Journal of Learning Disabilities*, 23, 149-158.
- Fuligni, A. J. (1997). The academic achievement of adolescents from immigrant families: The roles of family background, attitudes, and behaviour. *Child Development: Abstracts and Bibliography*, 71, 121-142.
- Graham, S., Haris ,K. R., Mac Arthur, C. A. & Schwartz, S. (1991). Writing instruction for students with learning disabilities: review of research program. *Learning Disability Quarterly*,14,89-114.
- Kaur, J et, al., (2009). Home Environment and Academic. *Journal of Reading Behaviour*, 23, 76-89.
- Kulshreshta, L. (1981). *A Study of Certain Factors Related to Differential Patterns of Achievement among Bright Students*. (Ph. D. Thesis, Agra University). Retrieved from <http://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in:8080/jspui/bitstream/10603/23619/.pdf>
- Kurdek , A. Lawrence (1988). Relation of Eight graders family structure, gender, and family environment with academic performance and school behaviour. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 80, 90-94.
- Miller, S. P. & Mercer, C. D. (1993).Using a graduated word problem sequence to promote problem solving skill. *Learning Disability Research & Practices*, 8, 169-174.

Misra, K. (1986). Effect of home and school environment on scientific creativity. *School Psychology International*, 3,24-39.

Bulgren, J. A., Hock, M. F., Schumaker, J. B. & Deshler, D. D. (1995). The effect of instruction in a paired associates strategy on the information mastery performance of students with learning disabilities. *Learning Disabilities Research and Practices*, 10, 22-37.

Lee, C. K., Maureen, N.,Phang,R. (1999, April). *A school based study of cooperative learning and its effects on social studies achievement*, Singapore. Retrieved from <http://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED434070.pdf>

Hughes, C.A. & Schumaker, J. B. (1991). Test taking strategy for adolescents with learning disabilities, exceptionality. *Journal of Learning Disabilities*, 2, 205-221.

Moody & Raymond (1993).Using a graduated word problem solving skill. *Learning Disability Research &Practices*, 8,169-174.

Robertson (1978). Relationship between learning strategy, attention deployment and personality. *The British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 36, 86-87.

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<http://www.shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in>

Vassar Stats.net (a statistical computation website)

<http://www.vassarstats.net>

Kerala State Literacy Mission Authority

<http://www.literacymissionkerala.org>

National Literacy Mission- India

<http://www.nlm.nic.in>